

Saponins from *Randia dumetorum* Lamk. Fruit Pulp

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The fruit pulp of *Randia dumetorum* Lamk. commonly known as 'Mainphal' yields six saponins named as dumetoronin A,B,C,D,E and F and four free sugars. The structure of all the six saponins have been discussed. Three of the free sugars have also been identified.

RANDIA *dumetorum* Lamk. commonly known as 'Mainphal' in Hindi belongs to the family Rubiaceae. It is used in the Indian system of medicine as emetic, antidysenteric and as fish poison¹. Recently, it has been found that it has antifertility property².

Vogtherr³ was the first to isolate the saponin, m.p. 250° which on hydrolysis yielded a genin and two sugars of which the osazones melted at 166-167° and 176-77°. Later on Gedeon⁴ isolated two saponins m.p. 260° and 289° and thought one to be the saponin and the other to be prosapogenin as both these products on hydrolysis yielded the same sapogenin, oleanolic acid.

In 1954, Chinese workers⁵ isolated a saponin which contained glucose, fructose, and glucuronic acid in the ratio of 1 : 3 : 3. Later on, Varshney and Sannie⁶ isolated a colourless saponin which on hydrolysis gave oleanolic acid, 1 mole of glucose, 1 mole of fructose, 1 mole of xylose and probably two moles of glucuronic acid.

In 1960 Atal *et al*⁷. isolated a saponin named, ursosaponin from the fruits of this plant which on hydrolysis gave ursolic acid. Recently, Dhar *et al*⁸. studied the bark of this plant and isolated two genins, randialic acid A (19- α -hydroxy ursolic acid) and randialic acid B (19-dehydro-ursolic acid).

In view of these conflicting reports a reinvestigation of *Randia dumetorum* Lamk. fruits was taken up.

The dried fruits obtained from the local market were broken into small pieces and the dry pulp was separated, powdered and defatted with light petroleum ether. The well defatted powder was exhaustively extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract on concentration and subsequent treatment and precipitation⁹ gave a colour-

less powder which gave all the tests for saponin. The saponin on TLC showed eleven spots. These products were separated on a column of silica gel (cf. Table 1). The first spot corresponded to free genin and was identified as oleanolic acid by m.p., m.m.p. and comparison of IR. spectrum with that of an authentic sample. The middle six spots were identified as saponins while last four as free sugars.

TABLE 1

Sr. Fraction No.	Eluant	Substance
1. 1-5	CHCl ₃ - CH ₂ - OH - H ₂ O (65 : 35 : 10)	Free genin (Oleanolic acid)
2. 6-18	-do-	Mixture of F, E and genin
3. 19-22	-do-	E
4. 23-24	-do-	Mixture of E and D
5. 25-30	-do-	D
6. 31-55	-do-	Mixture of D and C
7. 56-59	-do-	D C and B
8. 60-66	-do-	B
9. 67-76	CHCl ₃ - CH ₂ - OH - H ₂ O (65 : 35 : 10)	Mixture of B and A
10. 77-89	-do-	A
11. 90-92	(65 : 45 : 10)	A and free sugars
12. 93-100	90% Methanol	Free sugars

By rechromatography of the various mixtures, all the six products have been separated in pure form and all of them gave the tests for saponin. All the six saponins were obtained in the pure state and named as Dumetoronin A, B, C, D, E and F. The dumetoronin A, B, C and D were present almost in equal amounts while E and F were present in trace amounts. All the saponins were separately hydrolysed with 2*N* aqueous sulphuric acid and all of them gave oleanolic acid identified by mp, m.m.p. and comparison of IR spectrum with an authentic sample. The saponins gave difference in sugars identified by paper chromatography (cf. Table 2). This showed that all dumetoronins are the glycosides with the same aglycone (oleanolic acid) and have different sugars.

TABLE 2—SUGARS PRODUCED ON HYDROLYSIS OF SAPONINS

Saponins	Sugars produced on acid hydrolysis
Dumetoronin A & B	Glucuronic Acid, glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and unknown sugar*
Dumetoronin C & D	Glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and unknown sugar*
Dumetoronin E	Glucose, rhamnose and unknown sugar*
Dumetoronin F	Glucose and unknown sugar*

Dumetoronins A, B, C, D, E and F were separately refluxed with 5% sodium hydroxide for four hours. The reaction mixtures were neutralized with ion-exchange resin IR 120 (H⁺) and then concentrated under reduced pressure. Examination of these products by TLC showed a single spot in each case which corresponded to the original saponins indicating that -COOH group was free in all the saponins and the sugars were attached at C-3 OH group.

The crude saponin mixture was methylated with diazomethane. The methyl esters formed were separated on a column of silica gel (cf. Table 3).

The methyl ester of different dumetoronins were identified by separately methylating the pure dumetoronin A, B, C, D, E and F.

The methyl esters of dumetoronin A, B, C, D, E and F were obtained in pure state which on acid hydrolysis gave saponogens identified as methyl ester of oleanolic acid and the sugars as in the saponins. This confirmed that in all the above saponins the -COOH group is free and all the sugars are attached to C-3 hydroxyl group.

Dumetoronin D was methylated by dimethyl sulphoxide, silver oxide and methyl iodide. The partially methylated dumetoronin D thus obtained was subjected to two Purdie's¹⁰ methylation, yielding fully methylated dumetoronin D. The fully methylated dumetoronin D on acid hydrolysis gave methyl ester of oleanolic acid

TABLE 3

No.	Fraction	Eluant	Substance
1.	1-4	CHCl ₃ - CH ₃ OH (95 : 5)	Methyl ester of oleanolic acid
2.	5-7	-do-	Methyl ester of oleanolic acid and of F
3.	8-11	-do-	Methyl ester of F
4.	12-14	-do-	Methyl ester of F and E
5.	15-19	-do-	Methyl ester of E
6.	20-25	-do-	(90 : 10) Methyl ester of E and D
7.	26-34	-do-	Methyl ester of D
8.	35-45	-do-	(80 : 20) Methyl ester of D and C
9.	46-48	-do-	Methyl ester of C
10.	49-52	-do-	Blank
11.	53-59	-do-	(75 : 25) Methyl ester of B
12.	60-67	-do-	Methyl ester of B and A
13.	68-76	-do-	(70 : 30) Methyl ester of A
14.	77-85	Eluted with 90% Methanol	Free sugars and traces of Methyl ester of A

and six sugars, out of these four were identified by paper chromatography and GLC as 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose, 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose, 2, 3, di-O-methyl-L-arabinose and 2, 4-di-O-methyl-D-xylose. The two other methyl sugars could not be identified.

The partial hydrolysis of dumetoronin A was carried out under varying conditions (cf. Table 4) and gave the following results.

TABLE 4—PARTIAL HYDROLYSIS OF DUMETORONIN A

No.	Strength of acid	Time	Temperature	Products of hydrolysis
1.	0.1 <i>N</i>	1 hr.	60°	Prosapogenin, corresponding to dumetoronin B and glucose.
2.	0.2 <i>N</i>	½ hr.	95°	Dumetoronin B, one more prosapogenin, glucose and unknown sugar.
3.	0.5 <i>N</i>	1 hr.	95°	Prosapogenins, glucose, xylose, and traces of arabinose and unknown sugar.
4.	1 <i>N</i>	1 hr.	95°	Seven prosapogenins, glucose xylose, arabinose, and unknown sugar

These results show that dumetoronin A differs from dumetoronin B only by a glucose unit. This was further confirmed by enzymatic hydrolysis of dumetoronin A with β -glucosidase when only glucose was released and prosapogenin formed was identical with dumetoronin B. In the same manner dumetoronin B, C and D were partially hydrolysed with sulphuric acid. Dumetoronin D on hydrolysis with β -glucosidase gave glucose.

Some of the prosapogenins formed in the partial hydrolysis of dumetoronin A corresponded to the prosapogenins formed in the partial hydrolysis of dumetoronin B, C, and D indicating that all dumetoronins are interrelated.

On the basis of above results the following partial structures have been assigned to dumetoronin A, B, C, D, E and F.

Where R for Dumetoronin A and Dumetoronin B Glucuronic acid, glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose unknown sugar*

For Dumetoronin C and Dumetoronin D Glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and unknown sugar*

For Dumetoronin E Glucose, rhamnose and unknown sugar*

For Dumetoronin F Glucose and unknown sugar*

Free Sugars : Free sugars obtained by column chromatography (cf. Table 1) by elution with 90% methanol were evaporated under reduced pressure to a syrup which on paper chromatography showed the presence of four sugars. But out of these four, three have been identified as sucrose, glucose and fructose by co-chromatography with authentic samples. The fourth one could not be identified due to paucity of material and seems to be a higher saccharide than sucrose. It had slow mobility (R_f 0.43) than sucrose (R_f 0.77) on Whatman filter paper No. 1 in n-butanol-pyridine-water (6 : 4 : 3) and on acid hydrolysis it gave glucose and fructose. It is also possible that there is present only the higher saccharide giving sucrose which partially gives glucose and fructose.

* It is the same unknown sugar in all saponins.

Experimental

TLC and column chromatography were carried out on silica gel. at NCL, Poona, Paper chromatography was carried out on Whatman No. 1 and 3 mm filter papers using the solvents (v/v) : (S₁) n-butanol-pyridine-water (6 : 4 : 3), (S₂) n-butanol-ethanol-water (4 : 1 : 5) and (S₃) butanone-water azeotrope (100 : 17). The solvent systems used for TLC and column chromatography were (A₁) chloroform-methanol-water (65:35:10), (A₂) chloroform-methanol-water (65:45:10), (B) benzene-acetone (6 : 1) and (C) chloroform-methanol (9 : 1).

The spray reagents used were (a) acetic silver nitrate-ethanolic sodium hydroxide, (b) *p*-anisidine phosphate, (c) *p*-anisidine hydrochloride and (d) aniline hydrogen phthalate. GLC was done on AIMIL-NCL gas chromatograph using flame ionization detector and the column of 3% ECNSS-M on chromosorb-W. The purity of all saponins was checked by electrophoresis carried out on Whatman filter paper No. 1 using borate buffer (0.1 M) at 400 V for 4 hr. and stannic chloride was used as spraying reagent.

The defatted pulp was exhaustively extracted with ethanol which on concentration yielded a brownish powder. This on subsequent treatment with various solvents and precipitation gave a colourless powder of saponin. This on TLC showed eleven spots, out of these six were identified as saponin, four as free sugars and one as free genin. The crude mixture of saponins on chromatography on a silica gel column (cf. table 1) gave six pure saponins named as dumetoronin A, B, C, D, E and F and a mixture of four free sugars.

The crude saponin mixture (2 gm) was twice methylated with diazomethane for 16 hr. at 5°. The methyl esters thus obtained were separated by column chromatography on silica gel (cf. Table 3).

Dumetoronin A : Dumetoronin A (400 mg) was hydrolysed with aqueous sulphuric acid (2N, 400 ml) by refluxing for 6 hr. and gave an acid genin identified as oleanolic acid (85 mg) m.p. 309-10°, methyl ester m.p. 196-98°, acetyl methyl ester m.p. 216-18° (cf. lit. oleanolic acid m.p. 310° methyl ester of oleanolic acid m.p., 198-200° and acetyl methyl ester of oleanolic acid m.p. 219-20°).

The hydrolysate of dumetoronin A was neutralized with freshly precipitated barium carbonate and deionised by passing through a column of ionexchange resins (Amberlite IRA 400 and IR 120 (H⁺)). The sugar solution obtained was concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrup. It was chromatographed on Whatman filter paper No. 1 in solvent S₁ and showed the presence of six sugars namely glucuronic acid, glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and an unknown sugar.

Dumetoronin A (50 mg) was refluxed with a 5% solution of sodium hydroxide in methanol-water (1:1) for 4 hr. It was recovered unchanged-

Dumetoronin A (50 mg) was methylated with diazomethane in the usual manner and gave the methyl ester of dumetoronin A (55 mg) m.p. 98° (decomp.). Dumetoronin A methyl ester (40 mg) was hydrolysed with aqueous sulphuric acid (2*N*, 50 ml) by refluxing for 6 hr. and yielded methyl ester of oleanolic acid (10 mg). The hydrolysate after neutralization and deionisation showed the presence of six sugars identified as glucuronic acid, glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and unknown sugar.

Dumetoronin A (20 mg) was dissolved in sodium acetate buffer (10 ml, pH 5.0) and a portion of β -glucosidase solution (30 mg. in 10 ml. water) was added to it. The mixture was then sealed in a glass tube and kept at 38°. The tube was cut open after 24 hr. and the solution was concentrated to a syrup. The syrup was examined by TLC and by paper chromatography and showed the presence of glucose and dumetoronin B (Rf. 0.41 in solvent A₁).

The partial hydrolysis of dumetoronin A was carried out with different strengths of sulphuric acid under varying conditions as described in Table 4.

Dumetoronin D: Dumetoronin D had m.p. 259-61° (decomp.) and Rf 0.71 in solvent A₁. 400 mg of it was hydrolysed with aqueous sulphuric acid (2*N*, 200 ml) by refluxing for 6 hr, gave an acid genin m.p. 309-10° identified as oleanolic acid (155 mg). The hydrolysate on usual treatment gave five sugars namely glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and an unknown sugar. Dumetoronin D (50 mg) could not be hydrolysed with a 5% solution of sodium hydroxide in 4 hr.

Dumetoronin D (50 mg) was methylated with diazomethane and gave methyl ester of dumetoronin D, m.p. 152-55°. Dumetoronin D methyl ester (40 mg) was hydrolysed with 2*N* aqueous sulphuric acid in the usual manner and gave methyl ester of oleanolic acid (20 mg) as genin and five sugars, namely glucose, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and the same unknown sugar as in the case of dumetoronin A.

Dumetoronin D (150 mg) was permethylated with dimethyl sulphoxide (10 ml.), methyl iodide (5 ml) and silver oxide (300 mg) under anhydrous conditions for 48 hr. and then by Purdie's method. Complete methylation was checked by IR spectrum. The fully methylated dumetoronin D was hydrolysed with 2*N* sulphuric acid in the usual manner and the methylated sugars thus obtained were identified by co-chromatography and GLC and showed the presence of six methylated sugars. Out of which four were identified as 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose, 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose, 2,4-di-O-methyl-D-xylose and 2,3-di-O-methyl-L-arabinose by Rg and RTg values.

Dumetoronin E: It had m.p. 301-3°, Rf 0.85 in solvent A₁ and was sparingly soluble in water. On hydrolysis it gave, oleanolic acid and glucose, rhamnose and the same unknown sugar.

Dumetoronin F: It had m.p. 306-6°, Rf. 0.89 in solvent A₁ and was sparingly soluble in water. On hydrolysis it gave oleanolic acid and glucose and the same unknown sugar.

The unknown sugar was found to be the same in all dumetoronin A, B, C, D, E and F and had Rf 0.87 in solvent S₁.

Free sugars: The sugar mixture obtained by eluting the column with 90% methanol (cf. Table I), was chromatographed on Whatman filter paper No. 1 in solvent S₁ showed the presence of four sugars which was separated quantitatively by paper chromatography on Whatman 3 mm filter papers in solvent S₁. It gave four fractions. Fractions (I), (II) and (III) were identified as fructose (Rg 1.1), glucose and sucrose (Rg 0.77) respectively by co-chromatography with authentic samples while fraction (IV) (Rg 0.43) on acid hydrolysis gave glucose and fructose, identified by paper chromatography. Further study of this sugar could not be done due to paucity of the material.

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